

INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY MANDI (HIMACHAL PRADESH)

A MINI-PROJECT REPORT
ON
“X-RAY DIFFRACTION”

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Introduction- X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) is a rapid analytical technique primarily used for phase identification of a crystalline material and can provide information on unit cell dimensions. The analyzed material is finely ground, homogenized, and average bulk composition is determined.

Aim of the experiment- To study the structural properties of materials using x-ray diffraction (XRD) technique

Apparatus/ material required- Acetone (C₃H₆O), material powder, XRD setup

Principle -

X-ray diffraction is based on constructive interference of monochromatic X-rays and a crystalline sample. These X-rays are generated by a cathode ray tube, filtered to produce monochromatic radiation, collimated to concentrate, and directed toward the sample. The interaction of the incident rays with the sample produces constructive interference (and a diffracted ray) when conditions satisfy Bragg's Law ($n\lambda=2d \sin \theta$). This law relates the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation to the diffraction angle and the lattice spacing in a crystalline sample. These diffracted X-rays are then detected, processed and counted. By scanning the sample through a range of 2θ angles, all possible diffraction directions of the lattice should be attained due to the random orientation of the powdered material.

Conversion of the diffraction peaks to d-spacing allows identification of the mineral because each mineral has a set of unique d-spacing. Typically, this is achieved by comparison of d-spacing with standard reference patterns.

All diffraction methods are based on generation of X-rays in an X-ray tube. These X-rays are directed at the sample, and the diffracted rays are collected. A key component of all diffraction is the angle between the incident and diffracted rays. Powder and single crystal diffraction vary in instrumentation beyond this.

Result—1) From literature, I find out the structure of BaTiO₃ at 300 K, 260 K, and 150 K.

At the room temperature (300k) the structure of BaTiO₃ is Tetragonal (P4mm)

At 260k the structure of BaTiO₃ is Rhombohedral (R3m)

At 150k the structure of BaTiO₃ is Orthorhombic (Amm2)

2) By knowing these structure , I draw all these crystal structure using vista software

(a) At 300k temp

h	k	l	x	y
1	0	-1	31.539	100.000

(b) at 260k

h	k	l	x	y
1	0	-1	31.6194	100.000

(c) at 150k

h	k	l	x	y
1	1	1	31.5853	100.000

At 300k , 260k, 150k graph between intensity and 2theta respectively-

3)-***Why BaTiO₃ is ferroelectric*** -Barium titanate (BT) has become one of the most important electroceramic materials among all the ferroelectric materials because of its versatility in multilayer ceramics capacitors (MLCC), positive temperature coefficient of resistance (PCTR) thermistors, piezoelectric sensors, transducers, actuators and ferroelectric random access memories (FRAM) and electro-optic devices. Substitution of other ions for host cations at the A or B site in BaTiO₃ perovskite cell leads to remarkable changes of its characteristics. By adding oxide groups of softeners, hardeners and stabilizers one can modify it. Softeners (donors) reduce the coercive field strength, elastic modulus and the aging effects and increase the permittivity and dielectric constant and mechanical losses. Doping of hardeners (acceptors) gives higher conductivity, reduces dielectric constant and increases mechanical quality factor and aging effect.

Discussion and learning-X-ray powder diffraction is most widely used for the identification of unknown crystalline materials (e.g. minerals, inorganic compounds). Determination of unknown solids is critical to studies in geology, environmental science, material science, engineering and biology.

Other applications include:

- characterization of crystalline materials
- identification of fine-grained minerals such as clays and mixed layer clays that are difficult to determine optically
- determination of unit cell dimensions
- measurement of sample purity

Limitations- Homogeneous and single phase material is best for identification of an unknown

- Must have access to a standard reference file of inorganic compounds (d-spacing, *hkl*)